
back to sequences

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Peterlongo

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`back to sequences` is a rust program for bioinformaticians. It's purpose is to find where a set of k -mers occurs in a set of input genomic sequences.

More precisely:

Given a set K of k -mers (fasta / fastq [.gz] format) and a set of sequences (fasta / fastq [.gz] format), this tool will extract the sequences containing some of those kmers.

A minimal (m) and a maximal (M) thresholds are proposed. A sequence whose percentage of kmers shared with K are in $]m, M]$ is output with its original header + the number of shared kmers + the ratio of shared kmers: ``>original_header 20 6.13 TGGATAAAAAGGCTGACGAAAGGTCTAGCTAAAATTGTCAGGTGCTCTCAGATAAAGCAGTA..``
In this case 20 kmers are shared with the indexed kmers. This represents 6.13% of the kmers in the sequence.

CONTENTS

1.1 Usage

1.1.1 Installation

To use back to sequences, first install it using cargo.

```
git clone https://github.com/pierrepeterlongo/back_to_sequences.git
cd back_to_sequences
RUSTFLAGS="-C target-cpu=native" cargo install --path .
```

Rust has to be installed locally:

```
curl --proto '=https' --tlsv1.2 -sSf https://sh.rustup.rs | sh
```

Note: Test the installation: `cd tiny_test; sh tiny_test.sh; cd -`

1.1.2 back to sequences parameters

Get the list of command parameters and options: `back_to_sequences --help`.

Note: See *Some basic use cases of back to sequences* for commands lines associated to typical use cases

Back to sequences: find the origin of kmers

Usage: `back_to_sequences [OPTIONS] --in-kmers <IN_KMERS>`

Options:

--in-kmers <IN_KMERS> Input fasta file containing the original kmers

Note: `back_to_sequences` considers the content as a set of kmers This means that a kmer is considered only once, even if it occurs multiple times in the file. If the stranded option is not used (default), a kmer and its reverse complement are considered as the same kmer.

--in-sequences <IN_SEQUENCES> Input fasta or fastq [.gz] file containing the original sequences (eg. reads).

The stdin is used if not provided (and if *--in_filelist* is not provided neither) [default:]

--in-filelist <IN_FILELIST> Input txt file containing in each line a path to a fasta or fastq [.gz] file containing the original sequences (eg. reads).

Note1: if this option is used, the *--out_filelist* option must be used.

The number of lines in *out_filelist* must be the same as *in_filelist*

Note2: Incompatible with *--in_sequences* [default:]

--out-sequences <OUT_SEQUENCES> Output file containing the filtered original sequences (eg. reads). It will be automatically in fasta or fastq format depending on the input file. If not provided, only the *in_kmers* with their count is output [default:]

--out-filelist <OUT_FILELIST> Output txt file containing in each line a path to a fasta or fastq [.gz] file that will contain the related output file from the input files list [default:]

--out-kmers <OUT_KMERS> If provided, output a text file containing the kmers that occur in the reads with their

- **number of occurrences**

or

- **their occurrence positions if the *--output_kmer_positions* option is used**

Note: if *--in_filelist* is used the output counted kmers are those occurring the last input file of that list [default:]

--counted-kmer-threshold <COUNTED_KMER_THRESHOLD> If *out_kmers* is provided, output only reference kmers whose number of occurrences is at least equal to this value. If *out_kmers* is not provided, this option is ignored [default: 0]

--output-kmer-positions If *out_kmers* is provided, either only count their number of occurrences (default) or output their occurrence positions (*read_id*, *position*, *strand*)

--output-mapping-positions If provided, output matching positions on sequences in the *out_sequence* file(s)

-k, --kmer-size <KMER_SIZE> Size of the kmers to index and search [default: 31]

-m, --min-threshold <MIN_THRESHOLD> Output sequences are those whose ratio of indexed kmers is in *]min_threshold; max_threshold]* Minimal threshold of the ratio (%) of kmers that must be found in a sequence to keep it (default 0%). Thus by default, if no kmer is found in a sequence, it is not output. [default: 0]

--max-threshold <MAX_THRESHOLD> Output sequences are those whose ratio of indexed kmers is in *]min_threshold; max_threshold]* Maximal threshold of the ratio (%) of kmers that must be found in a sequence to keep it (default 100%). Thus by default, there is no

		limitation on the maximal number of kmers found in a sequence. [default: 100]
--stranded		Used original kmer strand (else canonical kmers are considered)
--query-reverse		Query the reverse complement of reads. Useless without the <code>--stranded</code> option
--no-low-complexity		Do not index low complexity kmers (ie. with a Shannon entropy < 1.0)
-t, --threads <THREADS>	Number of threads	
		Note: if not provided, the number of threads is set to the number of logical cores [default: 0]
-h, --help		Print help
-V, --version		Print version

1.2 Some basical use cases of back to sequences

1.2.1 Basic case

```
back_to_sequences --in-kmers compacted_kmers.fasta --in-sequences reads.fasta --out-
↳sequences filtered_reads.fasta --out-kmers counted_kmers.txt
```

The `filtered_reads.fasta` file contains the original sequences (here reads) from `reads.fasta` that contain at least one of the kmers in `compacted_kmers.fasta`. The headers of each read is the same as in `reads.fasta`, plus the estimated ratio of shared kmers and number of shared kmers.

If the `--out-kmers` option is used, the file `counted_kmers.txt` contains for each kmer in `compacted_kmers.fasta` the number of times it was found in `filtered_reads.fasta`.

1.2.2 Using filters

```
back_to_sequences --in-kmers compacted_kmers.fasta --in-sequences reads.fasta --out-
↳sequences filtered_reads.fasta --out-kmers counted_kmers.txt --min-threshold 50 --max-
↳threshold 70
```

In this case only sequences from `reads.fasta` that have more than 50% and at most 70% of their kmers in `compacted_kmers.fasta` are output.

1.2.3 Specifying strands

```
back_to_sequences --in-kmers compacted_kmers.fasta --in-sequences reads.fasta --out-  
↪sequences filtered_reads.fasta --stranded
```

In this case, the kmers found in `compacted_kmers.fasta` are indexed in their original orientation, and kmers extracted from `reads.fasta` are queried in their original orientation.

Note: Without the `--stranded` option, all kmers (indexed and queried) are considered in their canonical form.

One may be interested in finding kmers from the reverse complement of the queried sequences. In this case we add the `--query-reverse` option together with the `--stranded` option:

```
back_to_sequences --in-kmers compacted_kmers.fasta --in-sequences reads.fasta --out-  
↪sequences filtered_reads.fasta --stranded
```

1.2.4 Reading sequences from standard input

```
cat reads.fasta | back_to_sequences --in-kmers compacted_kmers.fasta --out-sequences_  
↪filtered_reads.fasta
```

Note: When reading sequences from standard input, do not provide the `--in-sequences`

1.2.5 Using several input read sets

Say you have three input read files `1.fa`, `2.fa`, `3.fa` to which you wish to apply `back_to_sequences`.

1. create an input and an output files:
2. run `back_to_sequences`

1.2.6 Output matching kmers

Output the list of matching kmers with their number of occurrences

`back_to_sequences` enables to output for each kmers in `in-kmers` set, its number of occurrences in the queried sequences.

In this case the `out_kmers.txt` file contains, for each kmer from `kmer.fa` its number of occurrences in the `sequence.fa` file (canonical or not, depending on the usage of the `--stranded` option).

Output the list of matching kmers with their position in sequences

`back_to_sequences` enables to output for each kmers in `in-kmers` set, its positions in the queried sequences.

In this case the `out_kmers.txt` file contains, for each kmer from `kmer.fa` its occurrences in the `sequence.fa` file. An occurrence is given by a triplet (`sequence_id`, `position`, `strand`). * `sequence_id`: id (starting from 0) of the sequence from `sequence.fa` where the kmer occurs. * `position`: position (starting from 0) where the kmer occurs on the sequence * `strand`: orientation of the canonical version of the queried kmer in the sequence. This is a bit misleading:

- without the `stranded` option, the position of the canonical version of the kmer is given. This version can be found in the same direction (`true`) or in the reverse complement direction (`false`).
- with the `'stranded'` option, the position of the requested version of the kmer is given. Only the forward version of this kmer is found.

Output for each queried sequence its location and strand of shared kmers

`back_to_sequences` enables to output for each queried sequence, the location and strand of its kmers shared with the `in-kmers` set.

In this case the `out_sequences.fa` contains for each queried sequence its usual header (original header number and ratio of shared kmers with the `in-kmers` set) and additionally, it shows the location (0-based) of shared kmers. For each location (including 0), the strand is indicated by nothing or a `-` character if the `--stranded` option is given.

1.3 Results

Results were obtained with `back to sequences`, version `v0.6.5`.

1.3.1 Benchmark on synthetic data

Results

This benchmark is reproducible by running `generate_data.sh` and then `bench.sh` in the `benchs` folder. Running time is given by the `\usr\bin\time` command, considering the `real` field.

Presented results were obtained on * the GenOuest platform on a node with 32 threads Xeon 2.2 GHz, denoted by “genouest” in the table below. * a MacBook, Apple M2 pro, 16 GB RAM, with 10 threads, denoted by “mac” in the table below. * AMD Ryzen 7 4.2 GHz 5800X 64 GB RAM, with 16 threads, denoted by “AMD” in the table below.

We indexed: one million kmers (exactly 995,318) of length 31. We queried: from 10,000 reads to 200 million reads (+ 1 billion on the cluster), each of length 100.

Number of reads	Time genouest	Time mac	Time AMD	max RAM
10,000	0.7s	0.54s	0.4s	0.13 GB
100,000	0.8s	0.8s	1.2s	0.13 GB
1,000,000	2.0s	3.5s	7.1s	0.13 GB
10,000,000	7.1s	11s	16s	0.13 GB
100,000,000	47s	58s	48s	0.13 GB
200,000,000	1m32s	1m52s	1m44	0.13 GB

Reproduce the benchmark

```
cd benches
./generate_data.sh
./bench.sh
```

In case you are running out of space, you can limit the bench to a smaller number of reads by running:

```
cd benches
./generate_data.sh 100000
./bench.sh 100000
```

This will generate and bench only 10,000 and 100,000 reads.

After running the benchmark, you may remove the generated data by running:

```
cd benches
./clean.sh
```

Benchmark data generation details

We generated a random sequence s of size 100 million base pairs on the alphabet (A, C, G, T) . From this sequence s , we randomly extracted 50,000 sub-sequences each of size 50. We consider these sequences as containing the set K of k -mers to be searched. As we used $k = 31$, each subsequence contains $50 - 31 + 1 = 20$ k -mers. Doing so, we consider a set of at most $50000 \times 20 = 1,000,000$ k -mers.

We also generated six sets composed respectively of 10 thousand, 100 thousand, one million, 10 million, 100 million, and 200 million sequences, each of length 100 nucleotides. Each sequence is randomly sampled from s .

Generate data for testing

You may be interested by generating a specific data set. For instance

```
# Generate 1 reference sequence of random length 50000 and minimum length 100
python scripts/generate_random_fasta.py 1 50000 100 ref_seq.fasta

# Extract 1000 random "reads", each of length in [100;500] from the reference sequence
python3 scripts/extract_random_sequences.py --input ref_seq.fasta --min_size 100 --max_
↪size 500 --num 1000 --output reads.fasta

# From those reads, extract 500 random sequence containing the kmers. Those kmers are
↪stored in sequences of length in [31;70]
python3 scripts/extract_random_sequences.py --input reads.fasta --min_size 31 --max_size
↪70 --num 500 --output compacted_kmers.fasta
```

1.3.2 Comparing possible alternatives

Data

We used the file composed of 100 million reads as generated by the *generate_data.sh* script.

We extracted its first kmer as following:

Commands

We used *grep* version 2.6.0, *pt* version 2.2.0, and *ag* version 2.2.0.

```
\usr\bin\time grep $kmer reads_1000000000.fasta
\usr\bin\time pt $kmer reads_1000000000.fasta
\usr\bin\time ag $kmer reads_1000000000.fasta
```

Results

- *grep* required 44 seconds (real field)
- *pt* required 15 seconds (real field)
- *ag* was stopped after 400 seconds.

Results

1.3.3 Benchmark on *Tara* ocean seawater metagenomic data

The previously proposed benchmark shows the scalability of the proposed approach. Although performed on random sequences, there is no objective reason why performance should differ on real data, regardless of the number of *k*-mers actually detected in the data. We verify this claim by applying *back_to_sequences* to real complex metagenomic sequencing data from the *Tara* ocean project.

We downloaded one of the *Tara* ocean read sets: station number 11 corresponding to a surface Mediterranean sample, downloaded from the European Nucleotide Archive, identifier [ERS488262](#). We extracted the first 100 million reads, which are all of length 100. Using *back_to_sequences* we searched in these reads each of the 69 31-mers contained in its first read. On the GenQuest node, *back_to_sequences* enabled to retrieve all reads that contain at least one of the indexed *k*-mers in 5m17 with negligible RAM usage of 45MB. As expected, these scaling results are in line with the results presented in the previous Table.

Out of curiosity, we ran *back_to_sequences* on the full read set, composed of ~26.3 billion *k*-mers, and 381 million reads, again for searching the 69 *k*-mers contained in its first read. This operation took 20m11.

1.4 Methods and features

1.4.1 Methods

back_to_sequences is written in *rust*. It uses the native HashMap for storing the searched *k*-mer set, with alternative *aHash* hash function. This data structure is used to index each of the searched *k*-mer set.

Depending on the user choice, the original or the canonical version of each *k*-mer from the “reference-*k*-mers” set is indexed. The source code is unit-tested and functionally tested using tools from the Rust community.

At query time, given a sequence s from S , all its k -mers are extracted and queried using the HashMap. Depending on the user's choice, the canonical or the original representation of each k -mer from the reference set is indexed. Again, depending on the user's choice, for each queried k -mer, the original version, its reverse complement, or its canonical representation is queried. If the queried k -mer belongs to the index, its number of occurrences is increased. The number of k -mers extracted from the sequence s that have a match with the index is output together with the original sequence. As an option, in addition to only counting the number of occurrences of each k -mer from K in S , *back_to_sequences* enables to also record their occurrence positions and orientation and to output this information. Sequences are queried in parallel.

1.4.2 Additional features

A **minimal and a maximal threshold** can be fixed by the user. A queried sequence is output only if its percentage of k -mers that belong to the searched k -mers is strictly higher than the minimal threshold and lower or equal to the maximal threshold. While the minimal threshold enables to focus on sequences that are similar enough with a set of k -mers, the maximal threshold offers for instance a way to remove contaminated sequences.

The **file format** of the sequences to be queried can be provided as a fasta or fastq file (gzipped or not). They can also be read directly from the standard input (*stdin*). This offers the way to stream sequences as they arrive, for instance when they are obtained during an Oxford Nanopore sequencing process.

The output format of queried sequences respects the input format: if the input is in fasta (resp. fastq), the output is in fasta (resp. fastq).

1.5 Citation

Anthony Baire, Pierre Peterlongo [Back to sequences: find the origin of kmers.](https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.26.564040) bioRxiv 2023.10.26.564040; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.26.564040>

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  url = {https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2023/10/29/2023.10.26.564040},
  doi = {10.1101/2023.10.26.564040},
  journaltitle = {{bioRxiv}},
  author = {Baire, Anthony and Peterlongo, Pierre},
  date = {2023},
}
```

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